

Power as "Physical Force" in a Multi-Ethnic Setting - Folklore & Present Realities: A Case Study of the Misings and the Karbis of the Greater Bokakhat Area of Assam

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Power is a relevant, multi-faceted, and contested concept. According to French philosopher Michel Foucault, the constitution of power must be understood, in first instance, as the multiplicity of force relations in which they operate and constitute. Disciplines that study human society have often accorded high emphasis on power's different manifestations and forms. This paper seeks to study how power defined as "physical force" is perceived in multi-ethnic settings, through a case study of the Greater Bokakhat area of Assam. The study shall survey select folklore of the two tribes, one primarily of the plains and the other of the hills, respectively, the Misings and the Karbis, that hold stake in the aforementioned area. The trends deduced from the relevant literature shall be compared with the perceptions that the members of the living generations of these communities hold about physical force. The discussion shall reveal the continuities and breaks in the worldviews related to social behaviour among the Misings and the Karbis of the Greater Bokakhat area.

Keywords : Power, ethnicity, folklore, Assam, Karbi, Mising.